

Developing IN-CORE Community App: Web Application for Community Resilience

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Community Resilience

1. Current state

- Existing vs. Desired Performance
- Dependencies

2. Immediate damage

- Loss of Life/Injury
- Physical Damage
- Loss of Function
- Decision Support

3-5. Recovery Stages

- Social and Economic
- Repaired Damage
- Recovered Functions
- Decision Support

Interdependent Networked-Community Resilience Modeling Environment

IN-CORE

<https://incore.ncsa.illinois.edu>
<https://github.com/IN-CORE>

① Damage and loss; impacts of natural hazards on communities

② Interdisciplinary recovery with fully integrated supporting databases

③ Alternative actions to enhance community resilience & inform planning

IN-CORE begins with an integrated community model

Buildings...

Physical infrastructure

Power...

Water...

Transportation...

Economy

Social Systems (e.g. households, institutions)

Center for Risk-Based Community Resilience Planning

NIST-funded Center for Excellence

- **2015** Awarded 5-year Cooperative Grant for Center of Excellence to address Community Resilience
 - Science basis for performance and assessment of physical, social, economic community systems
- **2020** Renewal of 5-year CoE
 - Open-source platform to advance community resilience planning and continue research
- **13** Universities, students/researchers/faculties

Architecture

IN-CORE Development – Testbeds

Interdisciplinary teams establish linkages between physical, economic and social models and networks

Testbeds

Hindcasts

Field Studies

Centerville
EQ & Tornado

Seaside
EQ & Tsunami

MMSA
EQ 2 tiers,
Flood,
Climate

Mobile
Hurricane & Storm
Surge, Waves, Sea
Level Rise

Galveston
Hurricane

Joplin
Tornado

Lumberton
Flood

Community Web Applications

Community Resilience Planning

This graph shows the framework used for matching and integrating the steps of the NIST's Community Resilience Planning Guide for Buildings and Infrastructure Systems (Playbook) with modules in IN-CORE. NIST's Resilience Planning Playbook is a practical, flexible methodology to set priorities, allocate resources, and manage risks to improve resilience. IN-CORE can provide data and analyses for multiple aspects of community infrastructure for recovery and resilience planning. This integrative framework matches the planning steps with the appropriate data outputs or models within IN-CORE. For example, Step 2 of the Playbook, Understand the Situation is a planning step that draws information from built environment, social, economic, impact, and recovery inventories developed in IN-CORE such as buildings inventory, housing units, household allocation inventory. IN-CORE community description inventories also support Step 3 of the Playbook process, Determine Goals and Objectives. The next phase of this framework integrates IN-CORE's predictive models of hazard, damages, social and economic impacts, and recovery with Step 4 of the Playbook, Plan development where user communities can develop strategies, policies, actions to achieve their resilience goals and objectives based on the predictions provided by various IN-CORE models such as expected building damages, population displacement, employment losses. Plan development (Step 4) also relies on the capability of IN-CORE modules to present the expected outcomes of various mitigation and recovery policies in order to reduce damages and losses and improve recovery proactively in advance of predicted hazard scenarios. Together the data and analysis capabilities of IN-CORE and the planning process of the Playbook are integrated to support and inform planning with analysis and modeling.

Integrating the Playbook and IN-CORE

IN-CORE MODEL

- STEP 1 Start
- STEP 2 Community description, built, social, impact, recovery
- STEP 3 Modeling: hazard, damage impact, recovery
- STEP 4 Resilience policies and decisions
- STEP 5 IN-CORE visualization and web interface

PLAYBOOK

- STEP 1 Form a collaborative planning team
- STEP 2 Understand the situation
- STEP 3 Determine goals and objectives
- STEP 4 Plan development
- STEP 5 Plan preparation, review and approval
- STEP 6 Plan implementation and maintain

INTEGRATION

Logos for NIST, IN-CORE, and ILLINOIS NCSA | National Center for Supercomputing Applications are shown at the bottom.

Population Stability Economic Stability **Physical Services Stability**

Count of Functional Buildings

PLAYBOOK BUILDING CLUSTERS	PERCENT (%)		NO. OF BUILDINGS	
	FUNCTIONAL	NON-FUNCTIONAL	FUNCTIONAL	NON-FUNCTIONAL
Critical Facilities				
Medical - Health Care	7.3%	92.7%	3	38
Emergency Operations Centers	67.9%	32.1%	19	9
Critical Government - First Responder Facilities	87.5%	12.5%	7	1
Non-ambulatory Facilities - Prisons, nursing homes, etc.	-	-	-	-
TOTAL	37.7%	62.3%	29	48
Emergency Housing				
Emergency Shelters	-	-	-	-
Residential Housing	-	-	-	-
SFH and Multi-family	-	-	-	-
TOTAL	-	-	-	-
Housing / Neighborhood				
Critical Retail	-	-	-	-
Religious and Spiritual Centers	61.4%	38.6%	54	34
Residential Housing	46.7%	53.3%	11816	13465
SFH and Multi-family	-	-	-	-
K12 Schools	64%	36%	57	32
Child Care Centers	-	-	-	-
Hotels and Motels	-	-	-	-
TOTAL	46.8%	53.2%	11927	13532

Learn More About This Data

- Form Collaborative Planning Team
- Understanding The Situation
- Determine Goals & Objectives
 - 3-1. Identify Long Term Community Goals
 - 3-2. Establish Performance Goals
 - 3-3. Define Community Hazards
 - 3-4. Determine Anticipated Performance
 - 3-5. Summarize The Results
- Plan Development
- Plan Prep, Review, & Approval
- Plan Implementation & Maintenance

Created Hurricane

NAME	DESCRIPTION	DATE ADDED	SUBMITTED BY
Hurricane for Illinois	Hindcast of Hurricane Ie - 8 datasets	2022-11-07	commresilengal

Select Hazard Type: **hurricane**

Upload a Hazard Dataset

Name: _____

Description: _____

Hazard Datasets: _____

Buttons: Save, + ADD ITEM

IN-CORE Release

- Latest release: 4.6.0 (Released on Oct 11, 2023)
- IN-CORE landing page
 - <https://incore.ncsa.illinois.edu/>
- Source code at GitHub
 - <https://github.com/IN-CORE>
 - Mozilla Public License v2.0 (MPL-2.0)
- Conda packages
 - <https://anaconda.org/IN-CORE>
- Sign up for an account at <https://identity.ncsa.illinois.edu/register/BSKC2UKQPU>

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